

CDIO INTEGRATED CURRICULUM FOR YEAR 2 CHEMICAL ENGINEERING

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Abstract

This paper explains the initiative by the Diploma in Chemical Engineering (DCHE) at integrating three core subjects within Stage 2A of its curriculum, namely *Heat Transfer and Equipment*, *Fluid Mechanics* and *Rotating Equipment*. It starts with an explanation of CDIO Standard 3 Integrated Curriculum and Standard 7 Integrated Learning Experiences which form the basis of the present initiative. This is followed by a brief explanation of DCHE's existing curriculum integration effort, and presented in a form of a curriculum "map". Specifically, the notions of local integration and vertical integration is explained. Next, we introduce the present initiative which results from an outcome of a review process undertaken by the DCHE Course Management Team (CMT) to continually improve its curriculum. Specifically, the review outcome is a need to introduce a sequential course structure for the Diploma to better the graduate attributes desired by Singapore Polytechnic. Next, we explain the present initiative, which involves the horizontal integration of the three core modules mentioned earlier. This is followed by detailed explanation of the work done, including the changes made in the practical hours for the modules and assessment weightings. We also provide an example of an integrated assignment, and share a format for administering an integrated mid-semester test. We then present outcomes of a simple survey on students' perception of the integrated curriculum; which show that overall, students generally reported that their learning had improved using integrated curriculum. This is followed by discussions of the various issues and challenges faced, in particular how we handle various scenarios of failures in one or more of the integrated modules. Lastly, the paper presents some ideas for improvement such as the use of concept maps and essays as the team work to continually improve the curriculum integration effort.

Keywords: *chemical engineering, CDIO, integrated curriculum, integrated assignment*

Introduction

The Diploma in Chemical Engineering (DCHE) of Singapore Polytechnic (SP) had been using the CDIO Framework (www.cdio.org) to redesign its curriculum since 2006. Our CDIO-type DCHE curriculum was introduced in April 2008. In 2012, we undertook a review of our diploma after 5 years of CDIO implementation (Cheah, Phua & Ng, 2013) and also integrated the CDIO self-evaluation process into our existing academic quality management system to drive continual improvement (Cheah, Koh & Ng, 2013). One main outcome of the review is the decision by the Course Management Team (CMT) to introduce a sequential course structure in which the whole cohort of 120 DCHE students will all undertake to study the same set of modules within a given semester. The rationale is simple: based on our own experience implementing CDIO since 2007, a sequential course structure can better support our "CDIO-type" integrated curriculum compared to the "more traditional" flip-flop structure that used to be the dominant course structure in SP. Our own teaching experience and results from longitudinal study of student learning experience delivered under our "CDIO-type" curriculum convinced us that students just learn and retain better the knowledge and skills covered.

This paper describes our effort in executing a curriculum revamp that integrates three core modules from Stage 2A (that is Semester 1 of Year 2) of our 3 year curriculum under the sequential course structure, namely *Heat Transfer and Equipment*, *Fluid Mechanics* and *Rotating Equipment*. A key feature of the integrated curriculum is the use of integrated assignment and integrated assessment consisting of a mid-semester test which requires students to apply knowledge and concepts learnt in the three core modules.

CDIO Standard 3: Integrated Curriculum

Detailed review of curriculum and integrated curriculum had been provided by Cheah and Koh (2013) and is not repeated here. Suffice to note that the basis for our initiative is the CDIO Standard 3 which explain an integrated curriculum as one that was "designed with mutually supporting disciplinary subjects, with an explicit plan to integrate personal, interpersonal, and product and system building skills." The Standard also explains that an integrated curriculum should include

"learning experiences that lead to the acquisition of personal, interpersonal, and product and system building skills (Standard 2), integrated with the learning of disciplinary content." Integrated Learning Experiences are described in CDIO Standard 7, referring to "pedagogical approaches that foster the learning of disciplinary knowledge simultaneously with personal, interpersonal, and product and system building skills." Integrated learning experiences support the delivery of integrated curriculum by incorporating "professional engineering issues in contexts where they coexist with disciplinary issues."

Existing Effort in Curriculum Integration

The need for curriculum integration and existing effort in DCHE has been summarized by Cheah and Koh (2013). In a nutshell, these include:

1. Integration of technical knowledge across different disciplines, e.g. mathematics and sciences in chemical engineering, mostly in Year 1 and Year 2
2. Integration via capstone project *Plant Design Project* in Year 3 which deals with simulation of a chemical processing plant
3. Integration of C-D-I-O skills, i.e. skills in conceiving, designing, implementing, and operating an engineering product, process or system across all three years. This approach is aimed mainly at supporting our *Final Year Project* in Year 3
4. Integration of "generic" CDIO skills (such as communication, teamwork, critical thinking, etc) in selected core modules across all three years, using engineering practice (Koh & Cheah, 2013; Cheah & Yang, 2014)

A "map" of the integrated curriculum in DCHE is shown in Figure 1. The abovementioned DCHE approach to integrated curriculum can best be described in two broad categories: (a) Local Integration; and (b) Vertical Integration.

Figure 1: Integrated Curriculum in DCHE

Approach 1 explained above, in which basic mathematics and sciences (chemical, biology, and physics) are integrated into suitable core modules is an example of local integration. Likewise, Approach 4 (shown as shaded rectangles) is also a case of local integration, whereby CDIO skills are integrated into core chemical engineering modules via engineering practice. For modules with practical component (e.g. FMCB in Figure 1), this is done via laboratory activities using dedicated set of pilot plants. The disadvantage of local integration is that there is limited content integration with other core chemical engineering modules, as the different subjects are usually brought together (i.e. integrated) in the forms of questions before and/or after the practical session only. For modules without practical components (e.g. ENV in Figure 1), this is done via assignments or case studies; and extent of integration with other core modules is even lesser. On the other hand, Approach 2 (solid line with triangles in Figure 1) and Approach 3 (solid lines with circles in Figure 1) are examples of vertical integration, which is an approach that integrates several modules together by cutting *across several stages* of study.

Description of Work Done for New Initiative

For the current initiative, we carried out an internal review of our modules in our curriculum using the approach as shown in Figure 2. A key feature of the mechanism is what we termed the "cluster review of modules" whereby several module are jointly reviewed together, requiring the participation of team members from all modules involved.

Figure 2: Cluster review of DCHE Modules

An outcome of the review is a new initiative that focus on horizontal integration (dotted line with squares in Figure 1), which strives to bind together several core modules *within the same stage* of study. A combination of horizontal and vertical integration had been used by

various educators to improve student learning and engagement (see for example, Mills et al, 1996; Orkwis, et al, 1997; Barlow, 2011).

In this new initiative, three core modules from Stage 2A namely *Heat Transfer and Equipment* (HT&E in short), *Fluid Mechanics* (FM in short) and *Rotating Equipment* (RE in short) are integrated by having students completing eight laboratory activities. Prior to this, each core module has a Practical component of 15 hours, with five laboratory activities to be completed, hence making up a total of fifteen activities. There is therefore a reduction of number of laboratory activities that students need to complete. For administrative purpose, all laboratory activities are considered to belong to FM. Table 1 shows the L:T:P (Lecture, Tutorial, Practical) hours of the three core modules, where it can be seen that practical component for FM is 30 hours whereas for HT&E and RM now have zero hour.

Table 1: Changes in LTP for Stage 2A Core Modules

Module Component	HT&E		FM		RE	
	Before	After	Before	After	Before	After
Lecture, L	30	30	30	30	30	30
Tutorial, T	30	30	15	30	30	30
Practical, P	15	0	15	30	15	0
Total Hours	75	60	60	90	75	60

In computing total assessment of each module, there is a need to account for contributions to each module from the eight laboratory activities. Table 2 shows the assessment scheme for the three modules. Note that a new component for continual assessment (CA) is added, namely CA2, which is used for HT&E and RE for the abovementioned 'accountability' requirements. Note also that FM retains its LAB component as assessment for the laboratory activities for reason explained earlier.

Table 2: Changes in Assessments (in %) for Stage 2A Core Modules

Assessment Component	HT&E		FM		RE	
	Before	After	Before	After	Before	After
EXAM	50	50	50	50	50	50
CA1	15	15	15	15	10	15
CA2 (New)	0	25	0	0	0	25
TST	10	10	15	10	10	10
LAB	25	0	20	25	30	0
Total	100	100	100	100	100	100

We also introduced an integrated assignment whereby students have to apply knowledge from all three core modules. The integrated assignment is one that is based on the Rankine Cycle typically used in steam power plant, as shown in Figure 3. It is most suitable for this initiative as it had all the three components covered in the three modules: design of a condenser, calculation of power extracted from a

turbine, pump head and associated pressure drop calculations. Students work in group of 4-5 in order to complete this assignment.

Figure 3: Schematic Diagram of Rankine Cycle

The integrated assignment was designed based on the following learning outcomes:

- (1) Compute the power generated by turbine based on operating condition given
- (2) Design a condenser of a Rankine Cycle to meet heat exchanger duty
- (3) Compute frictional losses across pipe line
- (4) Compute developed head and brake power required for the pump in Rankine Cycle
- (5) Discuss how the selection in pipe dimension of condenser will affect the power requirement and develop head of the pump
- (6) Discuss the impact of using organic fluid instead of water in the Rankine Cycle on the environment
- (7) Discuss the trade-off of Organic Rankine Cycle versus Conventional Rankine Cycle in the context of sustainable development

Consistent with CDIO Standard 7, skills such as critical thinking, hypothesis testing, information literacy, and consideration of impact of engineering on society in embedded in the integrated assignment, in the form of learning outcomes (5), (6) and (7) respectively. It is also worth noting that the concept of Rankine Cycle is not taught in any one of the three modules. Basic information is provided in the assignment brief, and selected internet links are provided. Students are expected to explore on their own the types of organic fluids available and evaluate the performance of the Rankine Cycle when these fluids are used instead of water.

In addition, an integrated mid-semester test (MST) was implemented whereby students are required to take a common test with scenario that covers concepts of all three modules instead of the taking three independent mid-semester tests, one from each module.

Discussion on Revamp Outcome

We obtained feedback from students on their learning experience in carrying out the integrated laboratory activities. A questionnaire survey was

conducted on students' learning experience of integrated practical. We used a Likert 5-point scale whereby students are required to rate from a score of 1 ("Strongly Disagree") to 5 ("Strongly Agree") on the following three questions:

- Q1. Through the learning of the modules, I'm able to integrate the knowledge and skill learnt from each module and applies in different context.
- Q2. The conduct of the integrated practical sessions enhances my ability to see connections among these modules.
- Q3. The conduct of the integrated practical sessions enhances my ability to apply integrated knowledge and skills in similar scenarios.

A total of 83 students responded to the survey and the result is presented in Figures 4 to 6. The survey result indicated that overall, students' learning experience through the integrated practical was positive. 91.6% of the students agreed that through the learning of the three modules HT&E, FM and RE, they are able to integrate the knowledge and skill learnt from each module and applies in different context. More than 89% of students agreed that the conduct of the integrated practical sessions enhances their abilities to see connections among these modules. 86.8% of the students agreed that the conduct of the integrated practical sessions enhances their abilities to apply integrated knowledge and skills in similar scenarios. Currently, integrated practical is conducted every week and students have to submit report on the following week. A common feedback from students is that insufficient time is given to complete the report.

We analysed the performance of students on the integrated mid-semester test as compared to those taking three independent tests of the last two cohorts. Table 3 shows the comparison of the students' performance between Independent MST & Integrated MST. Figure 7 shows the mark distribution (upon 100) of students taking independent and integrated MST. It can be seen from the above that overall, the students' performance has improved as compared to the cohort taking independent tests.

Figure 4: Student response to Q1

Figure 5: Student response to Q2

Figure 6: Student response to Q3

Table 3: Comparison of the students' performance between Independent MST & Integrated MST.

	Independent MST*	Integrated MST
Mean	64.77	70.04
Median	65.33	73.00
Standard Deviation	15.50	14.94
Range	77.67	85.00

*average score of 3 modules

Figure 7: Comparison of Performance between independent MST and Integrated MST

We obtained feedback from students on their experience in taking the integrated mid-semester test. A questionnaire survey was conducted using a Likert 5-point scale whereby students are required to rate from a score of 1 ("Strongly Disagree") to 5 ("Strongly Agree") on the following three questions:

- Q1. I was able to answer the question in the time provided
- Q2. I was able to see connections between what was taught in the different modules
- Q3. The question challenged me to think

A total of 80 out of 116 students responded to the survey and the result is presented in Figures 8 to 10. The overall experience is a positive one. 81.25% of students agree or strongly agree that they were able to answer the question within the time provided. 82.50% of students agree or strongly agree that they were able to see connections between what was taught in the different modules. 85.00% of students agree or strongly agree that the question challenged them to think.

Figure 8: Student Response to Q1

Figure 9: Student Response to Q2

Figure 10: Student Response to Q3

Issues and Challenges Faced

In attempting to integrate the modules horizontally, the team faced a number of challenges. Some of these challenges are rather typical, for example meeting institutional requirements for the number of modules permitted per stage and the total hours per week. Other challenges are more unique, as least to the DCHE CMT. For example, in equitably allocating the “contributions” from each core module in an integrated activity, we have to study the learning outcomes of each practical and “parked” the practical score to the module which has the largest number of learning outcomes covered in the activity.

Another issue is the consideration of students who fail one or two of the three modules. Before the implementation of integrated practical, a student will repeat a particular module that he failed and have to attend the lecture, tutorial and practical session of that module. With the integrated practical, if a student was to fail HT&E and/or RE, there is no assigned practical session for these two modules in the timetable, hence the CA2 component of the two modules would not be available. The module team deliberated on this issue and finalized the allocation of CA2 scores based on various possible scenarios as shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Various Scenarios of Student Performance

#	Exam Outcome			Action for Lab Activity Marks		
	HT&E	FM	RE	HT&E CA2 (25%)	FM LAB (25%)	RE CA2 (25%)
1	Pass	Pass	Pass	P1, P2 & P7	P4 & P8	P3, P5 & P6
2	Fail	Fail	Fail	Repeat all modules		
3	Pass	Fail	Pass		Repeat module but marks retained	
4	Pass	Pass	Fail			Repeat module but marks retained
5	Pass	Fail	Fail		Repeat module but marks retained	Repeat module but marks retained
6	Fail	Pass	Pass	Repeat module and redo P1, P2 & P7		
7	Fail	Pass	Fail	Repeat module and redo P1, P2 & P7		Repeat module and redo P3, P5 & P6
8	Fail	Fail	Pass	Repeat module and redo P1, P2 & P7	Repeat module and redo P4 & P5	

Integrating curriculum, regardless of whether horizontal or vertical, requires more discussion and coordination among all the lecturers involved. Equally important is staff development for those lecturers tasked with delivering it (Malik & Malik, 2011). To this end, the third author developed a lecturer's resource for her teaching team, familiarizing them with the laboratory activities, as well as their roles and responsibilities.

Areas of Improvement

Bordogna et al (1993) noted that the "intellectual mission of educators must include the cultivation of each student's ability to bridge the boundaries between disciplines and make the connections that produce deeper insights". To this end, the module team will continue to improve on the practical design of the laboratory activities based on the feedback obtained. Several areas for improvement have been identified to achieve further curriculum integration. One possible area is the use of concept maps (Perkins, 1991) to assess the achievement of the intended outcomes in an integrated curriculum. We recognize that this practice had not been employed in our curriculum; and both lecturers and students need to be adequately trained on how to draw concept maps in order for it to be a fair and valid assessment. Longer essays have also been suggested as a means for assessing students' integration of knowledge from a problem-based learning case (Brauer & Ferguson, 2015) or written reports of weekly learning issues. These approaches are useful in making explicit students' understanding of the subjects taught. As noted by Crooks (1988): "Too much emphasis has been placed on the grading function of evaluation and too little on its role in assisting students to learn". We will explore ways to use these assessments formatively to help students improve their learning of the core modules.

Conclusion

Perhaps the most discouraging commonality observed in the literature on integrated curricula is the scarcity of published long-term effectiveness of such efforts. Useful retrospective reviews are available but are often limited to opinions based on group consensus or surveys (Brauer & Ferguson, 2015). However, based on the feedback from the students, the integrated approach does help them to see connections between modules and challenge them to activate various thinking skills. The module team will continue to fine tune the approach to help students improve their learning.

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